

A Survey of algorithms for maximum matching in Bipartite and general graph

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Abstract

The matching algorithm is a fundamental and elegant aspect of the combinatorics field, exhibiting its beauty in various applications, such as coset representatives in groups or block-triangular decomposition of sparse matrices. This survey aims to explore and analyze two significant algorithms for finding maximum matching in Bipartite graphs: the naive algorithm and the Hopcroft-Karp algorithm, which improves the time complexity from $O(mn)$ to $O(m\sqrt{n})$.

1 Introduction

”The matching problem, a fundamental concept in graph theory, involves the discovery of distinct vertex-disjoint edges. When a graph can be partitioned into two halves with certain conditions, this problem can be seen as the task of assigning n individuals to m jobs, ensuring no two individuals share the same job, and each individual takes on only one job at most. The pursuit of a maximum matching corresponds to seeking a configuration that achieves the highest count of matched pairs. This optimization conundrum finds application in a plethora of real-life scenarios, including DNA sequence alignment, resource allocation, and transportation planning.

This survey aims to comprehensively explore a selection of the most prominent algorithms within both the bipartite graph and general graph contexts. The structure of this survey is tripartite: it comprises Preliminaries, a discussion of the Naive and Hopcroft-Karp algorithms for maximum matching in bipartite cases, and an examination of the Blossom algorithm for general graphs.”

2 Preliminaries

We will introduce some graph notations which will be used in this survey, and then will walk through definitions and lemmas for the purpose analyzing correctness and time complexity of algorithms.

Definition 2.1. *Let $G = (V, E)$ be graph with set of edges E and vertices V . Denote edge by (u, w) where u and w are vertices. A bipartite graph is a special type of graph whose vertices can be partitioned into two sets such that two vertices within one set do not share an edge. Denote a bipartite graph by $G = (L, R, E)$ where L and R abbreviate left and right sides of the graph. Also Let $N[u], u \in L$ be the neighbors¹ of vertex u in L .*

¹neighbor of vertex v are all vertices u such that edge (u, v) exist

Fig. 1. Bipartite graph.

Lemma 2.2. *A graph is a bipartite graph if and only if it contains no cycle of odd length*

Proof. Assume that bipartite graph G has an odd length cycle $C = \{(v_1, v_2), (v_2, v_3), \dots, (v_{2k}, v_{2k+1}), (v_{2k+1}, v_1)\}$. WLOG, let $v_1 \in L$, then by definition of bipartite graph, $v_2 \in R, \dots, v_{2k+1} \in L, v_1 \in R$, which is a contradiction.

To show that a graph with no cycle of odd length is a bipartite graph, first decompose graph G into separate connected components. If each of the components is bipartite, then so is G . Consider an arbitrary component C with some initial vertex v in it. Assign v to L , neighbors of v to R , and alternatively assign vertices with odd and even distance from v to side L and R . Since C is a connected component, all vertices will be either be assigned to L or R . If there exists an edge connecting two vertices u and w on the same sides, then since the path from v to u and the path from v to w have the same parity, the subgraph made of this edge, the path from v to u , the path from v to w will form a cycle of odd length. $\square$

Definition 2.3. *A set $M \in E$ is a **matching** if any vertex in V is incident to at most one edge in M . A vertex is **free** if it is not the endpoint of any edge in M . A matching is maximum if its cardinality is the maximum among all the matching. Also denote the array contains matching of vertex v (if exist) by $M = M[v]$*

Fig. 2. An example of matching M denoted by set of green edges, v is free vertex.

Definition 2.4. *A path is called **augmenting path** relative to a matching M if its end vertices are free and its edges are alternating in M and $E \setminus M$. Formally, path $P = \{(v_1, v_2), (v_2, v_3), \dots, (v_{n-1}, v_n)\}$, is augmenting if v_1 and v_n are free vertices and set $\{(v_1, v_2), (v_3, v_4), \dots\} \in E \setminus M$, and $\{(v_2, v_3), (v_4, v_5), \dots\} \in M$.*

Fig. 3. Matching M (green edges) and its augmenting path (union of blue and green edges).

Denote $A \oplus B = A \setminus B + B \setminus A$ be the symmetric difference between two sets. It is easy to realize that if P is an augmenting path relative to a matching M , then $P \oplus M$ is also a matching.

Lemma 2.5. *Let P be an augmenting path relative to matching M , then $P \oplus M$ is also a matching and $|P \oplus M| = |M| + 1$.*

Proof. First we will show that $P \oplus M$ is indeed a matching. Let $P = \{(v_1, v_2), (v_2, v_3), \dots, (v_{n-1}, v_n)\}$, $P \cap M = (v_2, v_3), (v_4, v_5), \dots$, then $P \oplus M = P \setminus M + M \setminus P = \{(v_1, v_2), (v_3, v_4), \dots\} + M \setminus P$, which is also a matching since taking away any edges of a matching M still remain a matching. To show that $|P \oplus M| = |M| + 1$, note that P has odd length, and $P \setminus M$ has size $\frac{(n+1)}{2}$ while $P \cap M$ has size $\frac{(n-1)}{2}$. □

Lemma 2.6. *A matching is maximum if and only if it has no augmenting path*

Proof. The only if direction is straightforward: assume that a maximum matching M has augmenting path P , then $|M \oplus P| = |M| + 1$, which is a contradiction. Now assume that a matching M has no augmenting path but is not a maximum matching. Denote M' be a maximum matching. Consider graph $M' \oplus M$. Observe that each component of this graph is either:

- a vertex
- a cycle with alternating edges in $M \setminus M'$ and $M' \setminus M$
- a path with alternating edge in M and M' .

Note that cycle C in $M' \oplus M$, has even length by **Lemma 1.2**, and $|M \cap C| = |M' \cap C|$. Thus if $|M| < |M'|$, there exists a path P such that $|M \cap P| < |M' \cap P|$, or more precisely, $|M \cap P| + 1 = |M' \cap P|$ because of the alternating property. Therefore, this path is also an augmenting path of M itself, contradicting to previous assumption. □

3 Algorithm

3.1 Naive approach

From previous lemmas, it is natural to come up with algorithm to find maximum bipartite matching by keep searching for augmenting path and update current matching by performing graph symmetric difference operator.

```

1 def MaximumBipartite ( $G, E$ ):
2    $M = \emptyset$ ;
3   while True do
4     if exist augmenting path P then
5        $M = M \oplus P$ 
6     else
7       break
8   return  $M$ 

```

To search for augmenting path, we can use **DFS** (or **BFS**) and loop over unmatched vertices on L during each iteration.

Let m and n be number of edges and vertices of G . We can assume that $m > n/2$ otherwise there would be an isolated vertex and can leave out that vertex. For analysing running time of *NaiveMaximumBipartite*, note that while loop at line 4 runs at most $n/2$ times, for loop at line 7 is $O(n)$, for loop at line 8 is $O(n)$, running times of Augment call at line 10 is equivalent to DFS= $O(m+n)=O(m)$, so running time overall would be $O(mn^2)$.

Note that there are traversal overlapping in *Augmenting* function in *NaiveMaximumBipartite* algorithm above. If we imagine that there are two more vertices s (source) and t (target), and there are edges connecting s with vertices in L , t with vertices in R , then an augmenting path relative to a matching M is equivalent to a directed path from L to R . Finding this path by *DFS* require $O(m+n)$, so if there are $O(n)$ iterations, the time complexity would be $O(mn)$. Detail of this *ImproveMaximumBipartite* algorithm could be found below/

3.2 Hopcroft-Karp algorithm

The high level idea of Hopcroft-Karp algorithm is to improve the naive algorithm above by reducing the number of outer iterations. This is done by grouping augmenting paths with the same properties at each stage of matching. To begin exploring this algorithm in more details, first we will provide a new definition.

Definition 3.1. A maximal group of augmenting paths G relative to matching M is a set $\{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_k\}$ such that:

- P_i are augmenting path.
- If l is the length of shortest augmenting path relative to M , then $|P_i| = l$
- If there exist another augmenting path $Q \neq P_i$ with length l , then Q and $P_1 \cup P_2 \cup \dots \cup P_k$ are not vertex-disjoint.

Lemma 3.2. If M' is maximum matching and M is any matching, then there are at least $|M'| - |M|$ vertex disjoint augmenting path relative to M . Consequently, if n is number of vertices, then there exist an augmenting path with length $\frac{n}{k}$

```

1 def NaiveMaximumBipartite (L, R, E):
2     M = ∅;
3     hasAugmentingPath=True;
4     while hasAugmentingPath do
5         hasAugmentingPath=False ;
6         for u in L do
7             if Match[v]==None then
8                 for v in L, R do
9                     Visited[v] =False
10                    if Augment (L, R, E, u, M) then
11                        hasAugmentingPath=True
12                return M;
13 def Augment (L, R, E, u, M):
14     for v ∈ N[u] do
15         if Match[v]==None then
16             Match[v]=u;
17             Match[u]=v;
18             return True ;
19             // immediately augment when find free vertex
20         if Visited[v]==False then
21             Visited[v]=True;
22             if Augment (L, R, E, Match[v], M) then
23                 Match[v]=u;
24                 Match[u]=v;
25                 return True // recursively call until find free vertex, then
26                 perform  $P \oplus M$ 
27     return False

```

```

1 def ImprovedMaximumBipartite(L, R, E):
2   M = ∅;
3   hasAugmentingPath=True;
4   while hasAugmentingPath do
5     hasAugmentingPath=False;
6     for v in L, R do
7       Visited[v] =False;
8     for u in L do
9       if Visited[v] ==False and Match[v] ==None // During each iteration, a
          visited [] array is shared so that each vertex or edge is visited ,
          thus prevent overlapping then
10        if Augment(L, R, E, u, M) then
11          hasAugmentingPath=True;
12  return M;

13 def Augment(L, R, E, u, M):
14  Visited[u] =True;
15  for v ∈ N[u] do
16    if Match[v] ==None then
17      Match[v] =u;
18      Match[u] =v;
19      return True ;
20    if Visited[v] ==False then
21      Visited[v] =True;
22      if Visited[Match[v]] ==False and Augment(L, R, E, Match[v], M) then
23        Match[v] =u;
24        Match[u] =v;
25        return True
26  return False

```

```

1 def HopcroftAndKarpMaximumBipartite (G, E):
2   M = ∅;
3   while M has augmenting path do
4     Let  $G = \{P_1, P_2, ..P_k\}$  be the maximal group of augmenting path relative to M.
5      $M = M \oplus P_1 \oplus P_2 \cdots \oplus P_k$ 
6   return M

```

Proof. From **Lemma 1.6**, we know that each component of $M' \oplus M$ can only be one of these type:

- a vertex
- a cycle with alternating edges in $M \setminus M'$ and $M' \setminus M$
- a path with alternating edges in $M \setminus M'$ and $M' \setminus M$.

Since part of M in cycle C has the same length as part of M' in C , and if P is a path in $M' \oplus M$, then $|M' \cap P| - |M \cap P| \leq 1$. Thus if $k = |M'| - |M|$, then there are at least k paths with alternating edges in $M' \oplus M$. These paths start and end at free vertices in M' , so they are indeed augmenting path relative to M . $\square$

Lemma 3.3. *Let $G = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_k\}$ be the maximal group of augmenting path relative to M , and $M^* = M \oplus P_1 \oplus P_2 \dots \oplus P_k$ with $|P_i| = l$. Then if P is an augmenting path relative to M^* , $|P| \geq l + 1$. In other word, the length of augmenting path at each iteration of Hopcroft – Karp algorithm increase at least by 1.*

Proof. If we let $A = M \oplus (M^* \oplus P)$, then

$$\begin{aligned} M \oplus (M^* \oplus P) &= M \oplus (M \oplus P_1 \oplus P_2 \dots \oplus P_k \oplus P) \\ &= M \oplus M \oplus P_1 \oplus P_2 \dots \oplus P_k \oplus P \\ &= P_1 \oplus P_2 \dots \oplus P_k \oplus P = (P_1 \cup P_2 \cup P_3 \dots \cup P_k) \oplus P \end{aligned}$$

Since A by definition is the symmetric difference between two matching M and $M^* \oplus P$, and since $|M^* \oplus P| = |M| + k + 1$, by **Lemma 2.3** there are at least $k + 1$ vertex-disjoint augmenting paths relative to M . Since the length of these paths are at least l , $|A| \geq (k + 1)l$.

On the other side, if P and $P_1 \cup P_2 \cup P_3 \dots \cup P_k$ are vertex disjoint, then by maximal property of G , P has length at least $l + 1$. Assume that P and $P_1 \cup P_2 \cup P_3 \dots \cup P_k$ are not vertex disjoint, then P and $P_1 \cup P_2 \cup P_3 \dots \cup P_k$ has at least 1 common vertex v , thus share at least 1 common edge, which is edge contains v in $M \oplus P_1 \oplus P_2 \dots \oplus P_k$. This common edge is not in A , thus $A \leq kl + |P| - 1$. Therefore $(k + 1)l \leq A \leq kl + |P| - 1$, which imply $|P| \geq l + 1$. $\square$

Theorem 3.4. *Number of iterations of Hopcroft – Karp algorithm is at most $2\sqrt{n}$*

Proof. Let M' be the maximum matching, M_i be the matching at the start of iteration i . During the first $\sqrt{n}$ iterations, the length of the shortest augmenting path relative to M_i greater or equal to $\sqrt{n}$. By Lemma 2.2, $M' - M_i \sqrt{n}$. Since after each iteration, the size of matching increases at least by 1, imply that after next $\sqrt{n}$ iterations it will reach maximum size. $\square$

Since number of iterations is in $O(\sqrt{n})$, and the running time of each iteration is in $O(m)$, the time complexity of this algorithm is in $O(m\sqrt{n})$. To implement this algorithm, we should again imagine the original bipartite graph $G = A \cup B$ as a directed graph which edge from A to B is not in M and edge from B to A is in M . We also add imagined vertices s and t , and imagined edges from s to free vertices in A as well as edges from free vertices in B to t . Then we can use **BFS** from s to calculate shortest path from s to free vertices in B . Of all these vertices, the length of corresponding shortest path is also the length of the shortest augmenting path of current matching. One can refer to my implementation in Python in this [GitHub](#) repository

```

1 def HopcroftKarp ( $G = (L \cup R)$ ):
2    $M = \emptyset$ ;
3    $hasAugmentingPath = True$ ;
4   while  $hasAugmentingPath$  do
5      $hasAugmentingPath = False$  ;
6      $D = calculatePathLength(G, M)$  ;
7     //  $D$  is the array contains shortest path from  $s$  to other vertices in
8      $G$  ;
9     for each free  $v$  in  $R$  do
10    |  $d = \min(D[v])$ ;
11    // now  $d$  is the length of shortest augmenting path relative to  $M$  ;
12    for  $v$  in  $G$  do
13    |  $Visited[v] = False$ 
14    | for  $u$  in  $L$  do
15    | | if  $Visited[v] == False$  and  $Match[v] == None$  then
16    | | | if  $Augment(v, G, L, l, M)$  then
17    | | | |  $hasAugmentingPath = True$ 
18    | |
19    |
20  return  $M$ ;

```

4 End word

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```

1 def calculatePathLength(G, M):
2     queue =  $\emptyset$ ;
3     BFSvisited = [];
4     D = [];
5     for v  $\in$  L do
6         if M[v] == None then
7             queue.append(v)           // add to the end of the queue;
8             D[v] = 1;
9     for v  $\in$  G do
10        BFSvisited[v] = False
11    while queue is not empty do
12        v = queue.pop                 // pop from the start;
13        if v  $\in$  A then
14            for u in v.neighbors() do
15                queue.append(u);
16                D[u] = D[v] + 1;
17        else
18            if BFSvisit[M[v]] == False then
19                queue.append(M[v]);
20                D[M[v]] = D[v] + 1;
21    return D;

```

```

1 def Augment(u, G, D, M, d, Visited):
2     Visited[u] = True;
3     for v in u.neighbor() do
4         if Match[v] == None then
5             Match[v] = u;
6             Match[u] = v;
7             return True;
8         if Visited[v] == False and D[v] = D[u] + 1 then
9             Visited[v] = True;
10            if Visited[Match[v]] == False and D[v] < d and
                Augment(Match[v], G, D, M, d, Visited) then
11                Match[v] = u;
12                Match[u] = v;
13                return True
14    return False

```

References

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